

NIGHTLIFE JOURNEY OF CLUBBERS INSPIRES EMERGING DESIGNERS TO DEVELOP A VISIONARY CONCEPT CLUB

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ABSTRACT

The global design project of Heineken - 'Open Design Explorations Edition 1: The Club' - invited 19 emerging designers from around the world to co-create the club of tomorrow. To immerse in the nightlife journey, the design team connected with over 120 design-savvy clubbers in an online research community. Understanding the needs and emotions of clubbers was crucial in developing a visionary take on club design; triggering the senses and facilitating social interaction. By approaching this collaboration project from a service design perspective, the team was able to transcend the individual disciplines – interior, product, fashion, graphic and interaction design – in their creative process. In only one year, this project was taken from crowd-sourcing the design team and developing the briefing to the launch of the Heineken concept club at the Salone del Mobile 2012 in Milan.

Keywords: co-creation, consumer journey map, service design, online research community, interactive infographic

HEINEKEN, A BRAND WITH A PASSION FOR DESIGN

The historical legacy behind Heineken's design credence is what led the brand to pursue its progressive roots and encourage emerging designers. In 2011, the - in the meanwhile rather famous - aluminum bottle won a design prize during the Cannes Lions and Heineken is now even connecting with design beyond beer, by enhancing beer moments in a unique collaborative project. 'Open Design Explorations Edition 1: The Club' crowd-sourced young talented designers from New York, Tokyo, Milan and Sao Paulo to develop a pioneering

nightclub by inviting them to submit their portfolio via Heineken's Facebook page. Live presentation events in these 4 design cities resulted in the final composition of the design team, involving product, graphic, fashion, interior and motion designers.

HEINEKEN CONCEPT CLUB COMMUNITY

So far, Heineken brought the ingredients together that would lead to a beautifully designed night club. The real question was if all created concepts would be relevant in speaking to the emotions of clubbers. The project team at Heineken understood that in order to develop a relevant and impactful take on club design, understanding the needs and wishes of clubbers today would be crucial. That's the reason why, during the selection process of the young designers, Heineken and InSites Consulting were conducting a global research project with club goers to provide the design team with relevant and true consumer insights, acting as a briefing, a source of inspiration and a springboard for ideation.

Figure 1. The Heineken concept club community

Engaging a group of young, trendy clubbers from all around the world to participate in research can be quite a challenge and although the club of the future is an aspirational topic, the selection and execution of

the research methodology needs careful attention. We opted for an online research community (MROC) of 3 weeks with 120 participants for various reasons:

- A longitudinal piece of online qualitative research was the way forward as it makes it possible to conduct a global project, in which clubbers need to be ‘followed’ over a longer period of time, in a rather cost and time efficient way.
- The current generation of youngsters (Generation Y) are ‘digital natives’, the web is their second home. Talking to and working together with other people in the online space feels very natural to them (Van den Bergh, Behrer, 2011). In addition, the asynchronous connection in a community allows participants to join the online discussion on the time and location of their choice, perfectly fitting their lifestyle.
- Today’s consumers expect brands to empower them and involve them in both marketing and innovation activities. We worked together with people who were interested to participate and who could inspire us with interesting stories: design-savvy youngsters, living in one of the 12 trendiest cities on the planet (10 citizens of each city), going to a club at least one time a week and being a non-rejecter of the beer category in general and Heineken in specific.

In order to keep the community participants engaged over the course of 3 weeks we took them on a journey (Schillewaert, De Ruyck, Van Kesteren, Ludwig, 2010.). In 4 different rooms on the community platform they could share ‘their current clubbing experiences’, ‘the role of clubbing in their routine’, ‘their view on the ideal nightlife journey’ and ‘feedback on the first sketches of the designers’. The tasks presented to them were a mix of questions, writing reviews, keeping a (photo) diary and holding discussion battles. To develop a holistic view on the needs and emotions of clubbers, a movie metaphor was guiding the participants through the different weeks. From selecting the actors in the ideal nightlife journey, to the scenery and the scenario for the perfect night out.

REPORTING RESEARCH RESULTS FOR MAXIMAL IMPACT

The 3-week dialogue with clubbers resulted in over 2000 comments, providing a unique view on the meaning of clubbing in their lives. In order to report the outcome towards the designers in the most impactful way - a report that they would actually read and use during the creative process - we went beyond the traditional ways of reporting.

The analysis of the discussions resulted in the shaping of 28 insights, each linking a challenge for the design team to the needs of their audience. ‘Service design thinking’ inspired the integration of these learnings – spread over six touch points – in a consumer journey map. Following the definition of Stickdorn and Schneider (2011), a consumer journey map provides a vivid but structured visualization of a service user’s experience. The touch points where users interact with the service are often used in order to construct a journey – an engaging story based upon their experience. This story details their service interactions and accompanying emotions in a highly accessible manner.

Figure 2. Interactive consumer journey map: <http://nightlifejourney.com>

This ‘Nightlife Journey’ was reported as an interactive infographic (available at <http://nightlifejourney.com>), not only accessible on desktops, but developed in HTML5 with specific attention to iPad usage. The app guides the designers through the 6 phases of a night out – from ‘pre-club drinks and meeting-up’, ‘entering the club’, ‘going for a drink’, ‘dancing’, ‘chilling’ to ‘going home’ (Figure 2). To make the learning experience as engaging as possible for the designers,

the 28 insights were formulated as consumer quotes, emphasizing the emotions they experience during their journey.

FROM INSPIRATION TO CO-CREATION

The 'consumer journey map' was shared with the designers during a club tour of nightlife hotspots in the design cities, taking their observations of the clubbing environment and social interaction beyond the obvious. The immersion in the clubbing scene, combined with the knowledge of the consumer insights, inspired the team to come up with consumer-centered ideas that truly challenged the current nightlife experience.

In this phase, designers received specialist coaching from famous senior designers within their discipline; Mark van Iterson, Ramses Dingenouts, Eugene Bay, Henk Stallinga, Kim Leemans, Merel Wicker, Luc Schurgers, Sergio Fabio Rotella and prof. dr.ir. Jan Buijs. After the immersion in the clubbing scene and the kick-off briefing, designers and coaches joined the clubbers and the Heineken team on the online community platform, where they could spark ideas and share first sketches with each other (Figure 3).

Figure 3. DJ booth sketch by Lee Gibson as shared on the community

The project took full advantage of the characteristics of the online community platform; providing a 24/7 connection to stakeholders from all over the world for a longer period of time, supporting true co-creation. Mark Van Iterson, Head of Global Design at Heineken formulated it this way: "The community was our online hub, a kind of virtual creative lab. It was bridging all continents and time zones, stimulating cross fertilization. It kept the creative juices flowing through new progress, new insights, new briefs".

THE END RESULT: THE CONCEPT CLUB AT THE MILAN DESIGN WEEK

The interactive consumer journey map did not only serve as a briefing and a source of inspiration, the research also proved to be crucial for the senior designers in making the final selection of ideas to be part of the actual club. By taking the journey of clubbers as a starting point, the Heineken concept club – showcased at the Salone del Mobile 2012 in Milan – successfully took the design critics by surprise. From the lay-out of the club (Figure 4), based on the 6 phases of the consumer journey map, to the shelves where clubbers can leave their drink while dancing, the whole experience is designed to provide relevant and impactful answers to the needs of clubbers.

Figure 4. Artistic impression of the lay-out of the club, mirroring the touchpoints of the nightlife journey: 'Entering the club' through the tunnel, 'Going for a drink' in the green zone, 'Dancing' in the red zone and 'Chilling' in the blue zone

While most clubs currently focus on their entertainment value, the clubbers in the community reminded the design team that going out is also about hospitality: "To have a fun night out in the club, we really need to feel welcome. To start the night with a great vibe, I'm in need for a warm, fun and exciting atmosphere. The staff has an important role in making my night enjoyable!".

The fashion designers transformed the staff and dressed them other-worldly outfits matching the identity of the club and radiating positive energy (Figure 5). The hosts provide guests with a warm welcome, the waiters wonder around instigating playful dares to get them out of their shells and when it's time to move on, a friendly concierge guides clubbers onwards, giving directions and arranging cabs home.

Figure 5. Fashion design for the staff and the Heineken serving tray

Even the simple act of ordering a beer has been creatively deconstructed and carefully considered, anticipating on the need of clubbers to draw the attention of the bar man: “I often feel like the bar man is ignoring me while I obviously try to get his attention, I hate this!”. Tap a bottle-shaped icon on the interactive bar surface and pulsing, concentric circles attract the server’s attention and tell him that you have priority over the guy next to you. When your beer is served, the bar man taps the icon to explode it, showing that the order has been fulfilled (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Interactive bar surface

By connecting with emerging designers, taking inspiration from the nightlife journey of clubbers and approaching club design as the service of the ideal nightlife experience, Heineken pushed the boundaries and unveiled a visionary pop-up club, housing 9 consumer relevant design concepts and product innovations. The stimulating and progressive

environment was designed to trigger the senses of the audience and facilitate social interaction; it proved to be an exceptionally welcoming, memorable and conversational night out.

EVALUATION OF THE POP-UP CLUB BY THE MILAN CLUBBERS

The day after enjoying this new clubbing experience, visitors of the club during the Milan Design Week were invited for an online interview. Recruitment for this interview happened via Twitter and the database of people invited to the opening. In total, 23 club goers took part (15 males & 8 females). Overall, the club got a report figure of almost 9/10 and was seen as a surprising and innovative action of Heineken. Moreover, the concept club was perceived as a different and more entertaining experience than the one in a regular club.

Almost all reviews mentioned the link between Heineken as a brand and ‘design’. The interactive bar and the friendliness of the club personnel – both closely linked to the consumer insights – proved to be very memorable in shaping the nightlife experience. By selecting a relevant group of people and engaging them through an innovative methodology, clubbers from all over the world shared their stories and emotions with us. In capturing these in an interactive consumer journey map, a team of emerging designers was able to trigger the senses of the clubbers in an immersive club environment. When design connects with relevant and true consumer insights, it proves to be one of the most powerful tools to evoke a lasting impression and influence the perception of brands.

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